

Summary of *In Silico* Validation – Normal Atlas

	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
alpha-beta T Cells	0.9936	0.0304	↑
gamma-delta T Cells	0.9852	0.1227	↓
Central Venous LSECs	0.9937	0.0841	↓
Periportal LSECs	0.9931	0.0764	↓
Cholangiocytes	0.9915	0.1198	↓
Erythroid Cells	0.9586	0.4574	↓
Hepatic Stellate Cells	0.9901	0.1379	↓
Hepatocyte	0.979	0.1481	↑
Inflammatory Macrophage	0.9981	0.0202	↑
Non-inflammatory Macrophage	0.9817	0.2695	↓
Mature B Cells	0.9968	0.0327	↓
Plasma Cells	0.9328	0.4348	↓
NK-like Cells	0.9945	0.0611	↑
Portal Endothelial Cells	0.9928	0.0648	↓

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – Normal Atlas

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	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
T Cells	0.9863	0.0929	↓
LSECs	0.993	0.0882	↓
Cholangiocytes	0.9844	0.1731	↓
Erythroid Cells	0.9586	0.4574	↓
Hepatic Stellate Cells	0.986	0.2161	↓
Hepatocytes	0.992	0.0931	↑
Macrophage	0.9891	0.0979	↓
B Cell	0.9544	0.4347	↓
NK-like Cells	0.9925	0.1177	↓
Portal Endothelial Cells	0.998	0.1086	↓

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – Normal Atlas (Collapsed Subtypes)

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Summary of *In Silico* Validation – TME-Stroma Atlas

	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
B cells	0.9884	0.042	↑
CAFs	0.9798	0.1047	↓
cDC1	0.9948	0.0361	↑
cDC2	0.9847	0.1151	↓
Hepatocytes	0.887	0.2756	↑
Kupffer cells	0.9922	0.0738	↓
LSEC	0.977	0.1262	↓
LVEC	0.9855	0.1278	↓
LVEct	0.9868	0.1268	↓
Pericytes	0.972	0.1816	↓
Proliferation	0.9775	0.0741	↓
SAMs	0.9885	0.0611	↑
Stellate cells	0.9715	0.1444	↓
T cells	0.9793	0.1422	↓
TM1	0.9834	0.1473	↓
vSMC	0.984	0.1059	↓

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – TME-Stroma Atlas

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In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – TME-Stroma Atlas

Summary of *In Silico* Validation – TME-Immune Atlas

	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
B Cells	0.99	0.0356	↑
Bi-Potent Cells	0.9962	0.019	↓
CD4 ⁺ Cells	0.9953	0.1283	↓
CD8 ⁺ Cells	0.9952	0.1261	↓
T _{regs}	0.9914	0.0847	↑
Endothelial Cells	0.9996	0.0564	↓
Fibroblasts	0.9839	0.1091	↑
Hepatocytes	0.999	0.0872	↓
Mast Cells	0.9979	0.0928	↓
Myeloid	0.9956	0.0296	↑
Nk Cells	0.9986	0.0933	↓

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – TME-Immune Atlas

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – TME-Immune Atlas

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – TME-Immune Atlas

Summary of Cross-study Validation

Cell type (Reference atlas)	Pseudobulk (Atlas)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
Hepatocytes (GSE115469)	Hepatocytes (GSE146409)	0.963	0.0748	↑
Hepatocytes (GSE115469)	Hepatocytes (GSE156337)	0.9964	0.208	↓
Hepatocytes (GSE146409)	Hepatocytes (GSE115469)	0.9993	0.2514	↓
Hepatocytes (GSE146409)	Hepatocytes (GSE156337)	0.9903	0.4135	↓
Hepatocytes (GSE156337)	Hepatocytes (GSE115469)	0.9981	0.0601	↓
Hepatocytes (GSE156337)	Hepatocytes (GSE146409)	0.9486	0.1071	↑

Cell type (Reference atlas)	Pseudobulk (Atlas)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
B Cells (GSE115469, Mature B Cells + Plasma B Cells)	B Cells (GSE146409)	0.9838	0.1907	↓
B Cells (GSE115469, Mature B Cells + Plasma B Cells)	B Cells (GSE156337)	0.9975	0.2249	↓
B Cells (GSE146409)	B Cells (GSE115469, Mature B Cells + Plasma B Cells)	0.9799	0.4078	↓
B Cells (GSE146409)	B Cells (GSE156337)	0.9953	0.3854	↓
B Cells (GSE156337)	B Cells (GSE115469, Mature B Cells + Plasma B Cells)	0.9803	0.4065	↓
B Cells (GSE156337)	B Cells (GSE146409)	0.9498	0.3766	↓

Cell type (Reference atlas)	Pseudobulk (Atlas)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
T Cells (GSE115469 alpha-beta + gamma-delta T cells)	T Cells (GSE146409)	0.9985	0.0884	↓
T Cells (GSE115469 alpha-beta + gamma-delta T cells)	T Cells (GSE156337, CD4 ⁺ + CD8 ⁺ + T _{reg})	0.9986	0.0879	↓
T Cells (GSE146409)	T Cells (GSE115469 alpha-beta + gamma-delta T cells)	0.9936	0.3092	↓
T Cells (GSE146409)	T Cells (GSE156337, CD4 ⁺ + CD8 ⁺ + T _{reg})	0.9977	0.2352	↓
T Cells (GSE156337, CD4 ⁺ + CD8 ⁺ + T _{reg})	T Cells (GSE115469 alpha-beta + gamma-delta T cells)	0.9799	0.3099	↓
T Cells (GSE156337, CD4 ⁺ + CD8 ⁺ + T _{reg})	T Cells (GSE146409)	0.946	0.2875	↓

Cell type (Reference atlas)	Pseudobulk (Atlas)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Mean Absolute Error	Error Propensity
Hepatic Stellate Cells (GSE115469)	Stellate Cells (GSE146409)	0.9685	0.3595	↓
Stellate Cells (GSE146409)	Hepatic Stellate Cells (GSE115469)	0.9741	0.3896	↓
LSEC (GSE115469)	LSEC (GSE146409)	0.9698	0.2339	↓
LSEC (GSE146409)	LSEC (GSE115469)	0.9458	0.3989	↓
Nk-like Cells (GSE115469)	NK Cells (GSE156337)	0.9619	0.4516	↓
NK Cells (GSE156337)	Nk-like Cells (GSE115469)	0.9908	0.2223	↓
CAFs (GSE146409)	Fibroblasts (GSE156337)	0.7238	0.4811	↓
Fibroblasts (GSE156337)	CAFs (GSE146409)	0.9636	0.2564	↓

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – Cross-study Validation

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In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – Cross-study Validation

In Silico Validation of Cibersortx – Cross-study Validation

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – Normal Atlas

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In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – TME-Stroma Atlas

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In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – TME-Stroma Atlas

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – TME-Stroma Atlas

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – TME-Immune Atlas

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – TME-Immune Atlas

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – Other Cells

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – Other Cells

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – Other Cells

In Silico Validation of Support Vector Regression – Other Cells

